

doi:10.5281/zenodo.20006320

An Investigation Into The Impact Of Information And Communication Technology [ICT] In Teaching And Learning Islamic Studies In Tertiary Institutions In Yobe State With Special Reference To Zone C [Yobe North], Yobe State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This paper aimed to analyze the Impact of Information and Communication Technology in Teaching and Learning of Islamic Studies in tertiary institutions in Yobe particularly Yobe North. The specific objectives include: To investigate the effects of ICT facilities in teaching Islamic Studies, to find out how the use of ICT facilities in teaching Islamic studies enhances the performance of male and female students and to compare the performance of students taught using ICT facilities at pre-test and post-test and those taught using traditional method of teaching. Three (3) research questions were formulated to serve as guide for this study. The findings revealed that ICT facilities have a significant role on the performance of Students. In view of the findings it is concluded that effective use of ICT facilities in teaching should be employed as it will enhance student's performance of in tertiary institutions.

Keywords: investigation, impact, ICT, teaching and learning, Islamic studies, tertiary institutions.

INTRODUCTION

Information and communication Technology (ICT) is becoming increasingly important in today's world which is named information age because it is believed to be able to accommodate and speed up our entry into information based environment. In addition it should be accessible, relevant and delivered in an efficient manner. ICT is presently considered as a determinate factor for the success of one nation. It is a dynamic field, which has great impact on the society in several dimensions-ethical, social and political.

In Islam, any knowledge, idea, innovation in the fields of science and technology should be adopted, provided they did not contradict the teaching of Islam. And efforts should be made to bring them to the Muslim society. This is a communal obligation *{fard kifaya}*

The Prophet (SAW) and early Muslim scholars have possessed an exemplary model on how one should deal with the knowledge. They employed whatever available at that time to access information, store, and process and distribute their ideas and knowledge. Because of their positive attitudes towards knowledge, Islam emerged as a great civilization for centuries. Islam categorized knowledge into two. The first category of knowledge is that endeared by Allah to operate through revelation. This knowledge is regarded as the highest form of knowledge and eventually is made compulsory on every Muslim to learn, comprehend and implement. The second type of knowledge is that acquired by human via rational inquiry based on experience and observation, which normally concern with worldly matter. This latter form of

knowledge includes *tanzur* (observation), *tadabbur* (deliberation), *tathakkur* (recollection), *tafakkur* (consideration), *tabassur* (understanding) and *ta'aqul* (rationalization), all of which is mention in the Qur'an as mechanisms to gather knowledge. It is in the latter category lies the field of ICT. In this respect ICT is not alien to Islam. In fact, the technology have adopted and used-in a different way-by Muslim scholars in the early Islamic history. Hence, the usage of ICT to enhance the teaching and learning of Islamic Studies is merely not a new issue in Islam. Service and applications offered by the technology can efficiently be utilized in order to distribute and increase the level of understanding the Islamic knowledge.

Therefore great efforts are being made by Muslim scholars, scientists and intellectuals in evaluating the impacts of ICT on Islam, and at the same time, initiating ways to promoting Islamic Studies and information through the use of ICT. ICT is becoming a new engine for Muslims all over the world to collect, exchange, share and spread information about Islam. Services and applications offered by the ICT technology can be efficiently used in order to distribute and increase the level of understanding of Islamic knowledge. One of the greatest benefits to be gained from the use of ICT is Internet. It can be the most useful tool to disseminate Islamic knowledge and information and can be efficiently utilized in promoting teaching. Prevalent use of ICT by Religious studies teachers, particularly Islamic Studies teachers may be achieved by educating those of them who do not have prior knowledge of ICT. In Islam, the use of modern technology is encouraged as it helps in the development of positive thinking, the ability to innovate and drive for self-improvement. It is against this background that this study seeks to examine the impact of information and communication technology in teaching and learning of Islamic study in tertiary institutions Yobe state particularly Yobe North.

Statement of the Problem

It has been observed by Jimoh (NATAIS 1999) that Islamic Studies as a subject in Nigeria faces severe problems in relation to its curriculum content and delivery by the Islamic studies teachers. However it is unfortunate to observe that Islamic studies have been neglected by the learners and its content delivery by teachers has been too slow.

In view of the above this research work is set to solve the problems of academic failure in Islamic studies subject and improve the academic performance of students through the use of ICT facilities in teaching the curriculum of the subject by finding out the effect of the ICT facilities in teaching Islamic studies curriculum.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to determine the Impact of Information and Communication Technology in Teaching and Learning of Islamic Studies. The specific objectives of this study are to:

- 1) Investigate the effects of ICT facilities in teaching Islamic studies in tertiary institutions.
- 2) Find out how the use of ICT facilities in teaching Islamic studies enhances academic performance of students.
- 3) Compare the performance of students taught Islamic studies at pretest and posttest using ICT facilities and those taught using traditional method of teaching.

Research Questions

The study intends to provide answers to the following questions:

- 1) What are the effects of ICT facilities in teaching Islamic studies?
- 2) How does the use of ICT facilities in teaching Islamic studies enhance the performance of students?
- 3) Is there difference in the performance at pre-test and posttest of students taught Islamic studies using ICT facilities and those taught using traditional method of teaching?

An overview of Islamic Studies Curriculum

The survival and welfare of a nation depends largely on the way of life of its individual members, their moral and mental orientation and their cohesion as a society. This fact has been recognized in Islamic

studies curriculum which therefore addresses itself to the whole way of life of individual and society so as to achieve a balanced result.

A curriculum is considered to be a course of study in its traditional term many authorities have defined it in similar way. Walton et al (1976) defines curriculum as that content and those process designed to bring about learning of educational values, but Marsh and Stafford (1984) see curriculum as an inter- related set of plans and experience which a student completes under the guidance of a school. Yunusa (2008) asserts that it as varieties of learning activities that pupil engaged in under the guidance of teachers. Yusuf (2012) is of the view that curriculum is the totality of all planned and unplanned, guided and unguided learning experience learners are exposed to in a school setting for the purpose of attaining its educational objectives.

Meanwhile Islamic studies as a subject or course of study in a school has curriculum or in other words has varieties of learning experiences that learners are engage with but under the guidance of a teacher as observed by Yunusa(2008) and this varieties of learning experience in Islamic studies curriculum constitute the six inter connected topics to be learnt by students that include, Arabic alphabets, Qur'an, Hadith, Fiqh, Tauhi, Sirah and Tahadhib, as it is contained in the 9 years curriculum published by Nigerian educational research development council, Abuja (2007).

According to the curriculum published by Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council NERDC (2007) Islamic studies curriculum has been prepared to reflect its broad concern so as to include true and balanced value in the young Nigerians at an age when his mental and moral development is at a formative stage. The inner stability obtained and guiding principle learned will help him or her to stand firm in the midst of the cross current of ideas and rapid social change which are features of age.

On the other hand, Islamic studies can be defined as a totality of learning experience which is centered on the relationship between man and his creator and between man and his fellow men. However, Yunusa (2008) sees Islam as religion that creates a kind of direct contact between man and his creator to whom he owes his entire existence.

Information Communication Technology

I.T is simply be defined as a generic term that covers the acquisition, processing, storage and dissemination of information. It is the application of computers and communication technology in the task of information handling, information and information flow from the generation to the utilization levels. Information Technology is defined as hardware and software products, information system operations and management processes, IT controls frameworks, and the human resources and skills required to develop, use and control these products and processes to generate the required information (Greenstein-Prosch, McKee & Quick, 2008). Information technology was defined as computer software and hardware solutions that provide support of management, operations, and strategists in organizations (Choo & Shahryar, 2013). From the above definitions, it can be drawn that Information technology is a wide term on its own with a range of various definitions. But generally, it refers to any type of technology for the purpose of communication. The definitions provide explanations on the use of electronic devices and technology to manipulate information, noting that it is most common amongst firms and not in personal settings. It deals with computing. On a broader scale, Information Communication Technology (ICT), is often used an extended synonym for IT. It is a more extensive term that stresses the role of unified communications and the integration of telecommunications, computers, as well as necessary enterprise software, middleware, storage, and audio-visual systems, which enable users to access, store, transmit and manipulate information. This confirms the interrelatedness of ICT and IT, but stressing that ICT involves a larger scope than IT.

Components of Information Technology

According to Anonymous (2014), Information technology can be broken into; Hardware: this refers to physical, tangible and touchable components. It is the part that can be touched and seen. They can be further classified into 4 groups, which are:

Input devices:

These are hardware devices used to send data into the computer. Examples are light Output devices: these are hardware devices through which information is sent out of the computer. They include speakers, printers and monitors.

Central Processing Unit (CPU): this is the part of the computer that performs tasks as it comprises of the microprocessor which is the brain of the computer.

Storage devices: these are hardware components that store data. There are two type- Primary (stores information temporarily) and Secondary (stores information permanently). Examples are RAM and ROM respectively. Pen, keyboard and mouse

Software:

This refers to intangible components that can only be seen. They include computer programs and codes that control the hardware devices. A computer program is a set of instructions written to perform a specific task. There are three categories of software, they are:

System software; this provides the basic functionality of the computer. It is made up of the Operating system and Support system with Linux and Diagnostic tools as examples respectively.

Application software; this helps the users to perform specific tasks. Examples are Web browsers and Media development software.

Programing software; this is used by software developers to create, debug, maintain and support other programs and software. Examples are JAVA and BASIC.

Data:

This refers to raw fact and figures that are processed into information. They are generally stored in the electronic devices until they are needed. An example is NAME.

Procedures: these are the laid down rules and regulations that govern the way information is processed and exchanged.

Internet/Network: the internet is a global system of interconnected computer networks that use the standard internet protocol suite or other network to link several billion devices worldwide.

People: this refers to the man-power that is involved in the steps of IT activities. They probably determine the success or failure of information systems.

Elements of I.C.T

Computer Technology

A computer is an electronic device that is capable of storing and processing information in accordance with a set of instructions. Computer technology is defined as the activity of designing and constructing and programming computers. It has caused massive developments in the transmission of information. In these recent times, you either live with computers or are left behind. The usage of computers now brings about accuracy, precision and efficiency of data.

Communication Technology

Communication is the act of communicating- the share or exchange of information. It is a process of exchanging facts, ideas, and opinions amongst individuals. Communication technology is defined as the activity of designing and constructing and maintaining communication systems. This involves communicating using electrical devices. Due to the development of information technology, means of communication have also advanced with the use of telecommunication devices.

Telecommunication Technology

Telecommunication is the transfer of information across locations through electronic means. Telecommunication technology refers to techniques and devices that are used to transmit information over long distances via wire, radio or satellite without loss or damage of information due to interference or noise. The major trend now in telecommunications is a shift from mechanical to electrical, and in electrical, from analogue to digital modes of transmission (Anonymous, 2014).

Computer Communication Technology

Computer communication technology relays the convergence between computing and communication. Communication is the exchange of information. As computing is being done, information is being transformed and can be transferred. It is hard to distinguish where computing begins and where communication stops as they are both intertwined. Recent developments in computer and communication technology have led to a higher degree of information management.

Categories of Information Technology

Function I.T

This refers to technologies that make it easier to perform singular tasks. They enhance the efficiency of such tasks. These technologies are mostly used by accountants, which is most relevant to this study and other professionals such as design engineers and doctors. The most common forms of function IT are Word processors and spread sheets.

Network I.T

This refers to technologies that provide media for people to communicate. It is similar to communication technology as explained in the elements of IT earlier. Network technologies allow for users to interact as they want without limitations. They include emails, instant messaging and blogs.

-Enterprise I.T

These are technologies adopted by organizations to manage interactions among employees or with business partners. They are purchased and implemented by the organizations.

Using ICT in teaching Islamic studies

Islam gives great importance to knowledge and education, when the revelation of Quran began, the first word of its first verse is "Iqra" which mean "read" thus, education is the starting point of every human development.

The purpose of education is not just making a student literate but adds rational thinking, knowledge and self-sufficiency, in order to achieve this purpose effective and innovative teaching and learning methods are vital, especially in facing digital student's era. The digital revolution has resulted in one unintended consequence. Today's youth are actually much more media-centered than previous generation. In fact many people believe that the brains of today's youth have actually become reviewed to accommodate the thousands of hours they spend in front of computer screens watching and creating videos, listening to music, it has also been said that today's youth speak digitally.

Understanding today's digital kids and how they learn has profound implications not only for how teachers teach, but also, and perhaps more importantly, for how teachers reach them. Educational technology and ICT can be valuable tools when they are integrated into the curriculum appropriately to achieve learning gains, particularly when they are combined with a twenty first century curriculum. Teachers have to decide whether to try to pull digital students away from their native digital world or to motivate them by tapping into their digital world and using their natural inclination and inquisitiveness about what is digital (shelly et al2006). The choice here is in our (teachers) hands. However, if we want to continuously grasp student's attention make them happy to learn and create an exciting environment, we need to follow the current and not be against it.

In this case, the same goes to teaching Islamic studies, teachers need to make some adjustment on how the subject should be taught in order to make it competitive relatively. ICT is one of the tools that are able to suit the digital students' interest, make lesson interesting and enjoyable. Moreover, ICT is an interactive tool that combines a variety of elements including text, graphics audio, visual, audio-visual and animation that is able to arouse students interest Sahalu (2008). Most students are not only auditory or visual learners, but also multi-sensory learners. ICT has the ability to capture the attention of the leaners because it addresses a variety of learning styles. Shelly et,al (2006) stressed that today's students use digital media service in their daily lives. However, these devices or similar media technology should be woven seamlessly into their classroom experiences. By doing this their interest and attention can be captured and certainly achieve the expected objective of a particular lesson.

Originally, a ICT might have a tape recorder for audio and overhead projector for text, but as software and hardware becomes capable of and adept in handling more than one media, the term, multi-media was coined to define computer software applications and presentation that utilizes more than one media shelly et,al (2006).

Islamic studies is a compulsory subject for all Muslims students, it is aimed at teaching Nigerian citizens to have good understanding on Islam as a way of life and be able to resolve any difficulties and challenges. The main purpose of having the subject is to prepare Muslim students with strong Islamic foundation before they further their studies in higher Institutions. The challenges to the teachers here is what kind of teaching method should be used in order to increase students' interest? or at least maintain their interest, as such using ICT in teaching has the potentiality of performing this task.

Curriculum Implication of ICT on Islamic Studies

The existence of ICT into this world has brought a lot of changes in every human endeavor especially in educational sector and specifically in Islamic studies in effect, these changes demands the need to adjust Islamic studies programmes towards information and communication technology innovations so that both students and teachers will take initiatives in redesigning curriculum and making changes to meet the emergency need of IT.

Curriculum has a place in the relationship dimension of the environment, in that the students and teachers are focused on certain process and content in the curriculum and have a relationship with the curriculum and the methodologies that are associated with conveying the curriculum. Students and teachers may have very different relationship with different component of the curriculum.

In this case it is necessary to redesign Islamic studies curriculum in order to incorporate the modern information technology and ICT as this would enhance competence that will enable them enter and progress.

Riel (1998) observed that the use of ICT impacts on both declarative and procedural knowledge to such an extent, that clearly the current curriculum and learning were not designed to accommodate the increasingly rapidly expanding quality of curriculum to be positive, however, with the use of ICT students can be encouraged to address real problems and develop analytical and interpretive skills. The classroom can be transformed into learning community make it possible for many more people to be a part of the learning process in an open dialogue.

The effective teaching of Islamic studies requires facilities for its practical applications and support from school authorities for students, so that they can apply what they have learnt this has many aspects which include:

- The need for provision of a mosque or recognized place of prayer of Muslims so that the prayers is given its due importance.
- Provision of facilities such as ICT facilities (containing enough Islamic web-sites) to enable students send and receive information treated in the text books or class room.
- Due to the new approach in the Islamic studies curriculum/syllabus the federal ministry of Education need to organize re-training course on IT and Islamic studies for teachers of Islamic studies of secondary schools while colleges of education should be made to prepare their students for the effective handling of syllabus in one of their courses. Etubi (2009) opined that if Islamic studies must meet up with the new challenges in the era of technological development, manpower must be trained to fit into the modern office, the curriculum of Islamic studies education programme should be redesigned and enlarged to accommodate the new information technology.

CONCLUSION

Use of ICT in teaching Islamic studies concepts helps students to develop skills of listening, viewing and retain the concept taught for a longer period of time and at the same time apply it in their day to day worship and life. This means that the use of these facilities is superior to the traditional lecture method

which is dominated by verbal instructions while learning is mostly by memorization as cited by Udogu, Ifeakor and Ujelita (2007).

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher drew the following conclusion:-

- (i) It has been clearly stressed that the effectiveness of ICT facilities as a tool to enhance learning must specify; learning in a manner that is consistent with accepted learning theory, the subject matter being study, the population of students under consideration and the ICT element being used.
- (ii) It was established that lack of using ICT facilities in teaching and learning of Islamic studies made students to perform poorly in their academic work.
- (iii) It was established that use of ICT in teaching is not a barrier to the performance to both male and female student as such it is not gender bias or discriminative.

Since it has been discovered from this findings that lack of using ICT materials in teaching and learning is one of the major causes of students' poor comprehension, poor retention of concepts and poor performance in their academic pursuits, so the state ministry of education and educational Inspectorate Divisions among others such as non-governmental organizations like P.T.A etc. should consider the recommendations below. Hence it is agreed that ICT facilities play a significant role in motivating students to learn, interest them in the subject, yield better performance and made practicing teachers to have confidence in whatever concepts they want to impact to the students. Evaluation of Islamic studies curriculum should include the use of ICT facilities while schools need to be provided with these facilities to actualized societal, religious and moral development among the students and the general citizens of the society.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the findings in this study as enumerated above it has made it necessary to make some recommendations of certain measures which will help in the provisions, acquisition and enhancement of effective use of ICT materials in tertiary institution in Yobe State and Nigeria in general.

1. Government, school inspectors and heads of educational institutions should ensure effective use of ICT facilities in teaching Islamic studies as it has positive effect in the performance of students.
2. Both male and female students should be taught Islamic studies using ICT facilities by teachers as using ICT facilities is not gender discriminative.
3. Teacher should at all-time assess students' performance whenever new instructional materials is used to teach, as it will help in identifying the students' performance at different change of the instructional materials and its effectiveness or other wise of the materials used.

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